

COMPARISONS IN TOPOGRAPHY AND MORPHOMETRY OF UTERINE TUBES DURING THE FETAL PERIOD

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Introduction

The importance of studies dealing with spatial-temporal dynamics of transformations of the human organ systems during antenatal period of development is difficult to be overestimated for modern morphological science. A number of scientific works published in modern scientific periodical editions deal with investigation of these processes. The priority and importance of investigations of different organs and/or systems is not possible to determine. Undoubtedly, the study of embryo topography and perinatal morphology of the female reproductive system will contribute greatly in understanding of interrelations and interaction on shape-generating processes and spatial-temporal organization of anatomical structures, detection of time and morphological preconditions of a possible development of variants in their structure and congenital defects. Though even now literature contains disputable, fragmentary and non-systematize information concerning age morphological peculiarities of the organ systems of fetuses on the whole and uterine tubes in particular. Certain data determine that close shape-generating interrelations are established between the mesenchymal membrane of the paramesonephral ducts and caudal ligament of mesonephros (Wolffian body/inguinal fold) on the eighth week of development. Some other data determined that the mucous membrane of the uterine tubes during early reproductive age is covered with simple columnar epithelium with a small amount of ciliated and secretory cells available. Single lymphocytes are found in the submucous layer. The serous layer is presented by the mesothelium. At the same time, the muscular layer of the uterine tube wall is found to consist of the external layer (spiral), intermediate layer (circular) and internal one (longitudinal). Moreover, certain differences are found in the scientific literature in definition of terms denoting the origin of the embryo and formation of the paramesonephral ducts, the terms and mechanisms of occurrence of congenital defects of the uterine tubes; different data are contained concerning development of derivatives of the paramesonephral ducts. Little attention is paid to the investigation of the shape, length and diameter of the uterinetubes, histotopography of their walls in the dynamics of the fetal period of ontogenesis. Peculiarities of the structure and structural transformation of the uterine tubes remain a topical issue of morphologists and clinicians. A thorough examination of the perinatal processes of morphogenesis will help to isolate trigger components promoting development of congenital pathology. Defects of the urogenital system are third by their occurrence, including 5,4% of developmental defects of the uterine tubes. Determination of accurate and complete information concerning regularities of topographic-anatomical interrelations of the uterine tubes between themselves and adjacent structures during the antenatal period of human ontogenesis, specification of time and morphological preconditions of possible occurrence of their variants of structure and congenital defects is one of the important areas of anatomical science. An active introduction of ante- and perinatal prevention of congenital defects of the

internal organs requires modern approaches and methods of investigation of the antenatal period of human ontogenesis. Antenatal diagnostics, therapy, surgical correction and prevention of fetal pathology are the most considerable components of reproductive strategy and perinatology. At the present stage of development of perinatal medicine the main principle should be realized - attitude to the fetus as a patient.

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To find and compare tendencies of changes the uterine tube morphologic parameters in the two groups of fetuses remote in time, and determine age peculiarities of their topography during perinatal period of development

Materials and methods

The scientific study was conducted at the Department of Clinical Anatomy, Operative Surgery and Gynecology of Tashkent state Pediatric institute and it is a fragment of their planned scientific-research work "Peculiarities of Morphogenesis and Topography of the Systems and Organs during Pre- and Postnatal Periods of Human Ontogenesis". The materials of the scientific research have been considered by the TSPI Biomedical Ethics Board. The Board approved that the study was performed according to the "Ethical Principles for Conducting Research with Human Participants", approved by Helsinki Declaration (1964-2013), ICH GCP (1996), EU Directives № 609(24.11.1986), The experimental material (specimens of fetuses) was divided into two groups: I group - 35 specimens of fetuses deceased during 2021-2023; II group - 105 specimens of fetuses taken from the Museum of the Departments of Clinical Anatomy and Operative Surgery at Tashkent state Pediatric institute, collected during 1990-2010. Every group was subdivided into 7 subgroups according to 9 months of the fetal period of development (from the 4th to the 9th months). The age of fetuses and neonates was determined immediately after obtaining them before preservation by means of measuring the parietal-coccygeal length and parietal-calcaneal length according to A.A. Zavarzin, A.G. Knorre, B.M. Petten tables; recommendations by B.P. Khvatov and Yu.N. Shapovalov, A.I. Brusylovsky and G.G. Avtandilov. The choice of the preserving solution was caused by the fact that it is this neutral formaldehyde solution according to V.I. Proniayev et al. that least changes the colour of the specimen. The specimens of fetuses were first measured, preserved in 5-7% formaldehyde solution during 2-3 weeks, and after that kept in 3-5% formaldehyde solution. The specimens of fetuses from the first group were examined directly in the prosectorium of Tashkent state Pediatric Institute's "Pathologic-Anatomical Bureau" during planned dissections

Results

While examining peculiarities of the uterine tube structure at every stage of the perinatal period we have found certain peculiarities and regularities of their development. Particularly, regular topographic changes of the right and left uterine tubes, changes of their shape and histological structure were observed. Peculiarities of the uterine tube topography found by us should be characterized by a certain compliance with the ovarian topography, since regular interrelations in the development of these organs are found in the fetal period of human ontogenesis. Numerous studies dealing with investigation of the uterine tube

topography of fetuses conducted by scientists and published on the pages of periodical scientific editions are indicative of certain unconformity of results. Specifically it is indicated that at the beginning of the fetal period the uterine tubes passing parallel to the dorsal-lateral abdominal wall in a free upper margin of the broad uterine ligament till the end of the fetal period descend synchronously into the pelvic cavity and in all the cases they are located on the level with the uterine fundus. At the same time, their skeletopia changes from the level of the 5th lumbar vertebra at the beginning of the fetal period to the 2nd sacral vertebra in neonates. We can agree with a thesis concerning a skeletopic change of the uterine tube position, but we cannot agree with the thesis about synchronous descending of the right and left uterine tubes to the level of the uterine fundus. We have determined that in 8 out of 15 examined specimens of the early fetuses (4-6 months of age) both uterine tubes were found to be in an ascending position, in 5 cases one uterine tube was in an ascending position and in 2 cases both uterine tubes were located practically horizontally.

Conclusions.

In 4-8-month fetuses the uterine tubes descend gradually: from the ascending position near the rectum to the iliac fossa or the uterine-rectal depression. Dynamics of both uterine tubes demonstrates a tendency to a relative enlargement of length of both uterine tubes among museum (archive) specimens of 9-month fetuses. The length of the uterine tubes of 4-7-month fetuses deceased during 2021-2023 was not found to differ reliably. Similar regularity was found in the group of fetuses aged from 8 to 9 months. The length of the uterine tubes of the archival specimens increases reliably every two months. In this group of fetuses the parameters of the uterine tube length aged from 8 to 9 months were found to differ reliably contrary to the length of the uterine tubes in the group of modern specimens of a similar age.

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